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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF BIOADHESIVE BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY OF LESINURAD TABLETS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to formulate and evaluate bioadhesive buccal tablets of Lesinurad using sodium alginate, sodium carboxy methyl cellulose and carbopol 934. The tablets were evaluated for weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, surface pH, mucoadhesive strength, swelling index, *in vitro* drug release, *ex vivo* mucoadhesion time and *ex vivo* drug permeation. Tablets containing sodium alginate as a polymer (F2) had the maximum percentage of *in vitro* drug release. The surface pH of all tablets was found to be satisfactory (between 6.5 and 7.43), close to neutral pH; hence buccal cavity irritation should not occur with these tablets. F2 batch was considered optimum based on good bioadhesive strength (02.60 ± 0.03 gm). The drug release from optimum batch followed zero order kinetics with Higuchi release. Drug excipients compatibility study showed no interaction between drug and excipients. Stability study of optimized formulation showed that tablets were stable at accelerated environment condition. Thus, buccal adhesive tablet of Lesinurad could be an alternative route to bypass hepatic first pass metabolism and to improve bioavailability of Lesinurad.

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INTRODUCTION

Bioadhesion can be defined as a phenomenon of interfacial molecular attractive forces amongst the surfaces of the biological substrate and the natural or synthetic polymers, which allows the polymer to adhere to the biological surface for an extended period of time^[1-4]. The buccal route is considered as the most preferred route in case of bioadhesive drug delivery system. Drug delivery through the buccal mucosa has gained significant attention due to its convenient accessibility. The buccal mucosa offers a relatively permeable barrier for drug transport^[5]. Drug delivery through the buccal mucosa has proven particularly useful and offers several advantages over other drug delivery systems including bypassing hepatic first-pass metabolism, increasing the bioavailability of drugs, improved patient compliance, excellent accessibility, unidirectional drug flux, and improved barrier permeability compared, for example, with intact skin^[6,7] attempts have been made to formulate different buccal mucoadhesive dosage forms, including tablets,^[8] gels,^[9] ointments,^[10] films,^[11] patches^[12] and disks^[13].

Lesinurad is an oral uric acid transporter 1 (URAT1) inhibitor indicated for the treatment of hyperuricemia associated with gout. It reduces serum uric acid concentration through the inhibition of URAT1, an enzyme responsible for reuptake of uric acid from the renal tubule, and OAT4, another uric acid transporter associated with diuretic-induced hyperuricemia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Lesinurad was gifted from Torrent Pharmaceutical Ltd., Ahmedabad, India. Sodium alginate and Carbopol 934 were purchased from Yarrow Chemicals (Mumbai, India). Magnesium stearate was obtained from RR chemicals (Khammam, India). Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) was purchased from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd (Mumbai, India). Micro Crystalline Cellulose was purchased from SD Fine chem. Ltd (Mumbai, India).

Methods

Preparation of bilayer buccal tablets of Lesinurad^[14,15]

Buccal tablets were prepared by a direct compression method, before going to direct compression all the ingredients were screened through sieve no.100. Lesinurad was mixed manually with different ratios of mucoadhesive polymers and microcrystalline cellulose as diluents, PVP K-30 as dry binder, for 10 min. The blend was mixed with Magnesium stearate for 3-5 min and then compressed into tablets by the direct compression method using 9 mm flat faced punches. The tablets were compressed using a sixteen station CEMACH rotary tablet-punching machine. The weight of the tablets was determined by using a digital balance (SHIMADZU) and thickness with digital screw gauge. Composition of the prepared bioadhesive buccal tablet formulations of Lesinurad were given in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of buccal tablet.

Ingredients(mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Lesinurad	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
Sodium alginate	50	75	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sodium CMC	-	-	-	50	75	100	-	-	-
Carbopol 934	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	75	100
Aerosil	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Talc	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Magnesium Stearate	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
MCC	186	161	136	186	161	136	186	161	136
Total weight	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450

Determination of physicochemical parameters

Weight variation

Ten tablets were weighed individually and then collectively, average weight of the tablets was calculated.

Hardness

Hardness test was conducted for three tablets from each batch using Monsanto hardness tester and average values were calculated.

Friability

The tablets were tested for friability testing using Roche friabilator. For this test, six tablets were weighed and subjected to combined effect of abrasion and shock in the plastic chamber of friabilator revolving at 25 rpm for 4 min, and the tablets were then dusted and reweighed.

Thickness

The thicknesses of buccal tablets were determined using micrometer screw gauge. Ten individual tablets from each batch were used and the average thickness was calculated.

Content uniformity

Five tablets were selected at random and were powdered in a mortar; and amount of powder equivalent to single dose was dissolved in methanol[21] by sonication for 15 min and filtered through Whatmann filter (0.45 μ m) paper. The drug content was analyzed spectrophotometrically at 281 nm using a UV spectrophotometer. Each measurement was carried out in triplicate and the average drug content was calculated.

In vitro release studies:

The drug release rate from buccal tablets was studied using the USP type II dissolution test apparatus. Tablets were supposed to release the drug from one side only; therefore an impermeable backing membrane was placed on the other side of the tablet. The tablet was further fixed to a 2x2 cm glass slide with a solution of cyanoacrylate adhesive. Then it was placed in the dissolution apparatus. The dissolution medium was 500 mL of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 50 rpm at a temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C. Samples of 3 mL were collected at different time intervals up to 6hrs and analyzed after appropriate dilution by using UV Spectrophotometer at 255 nm (Lubna et al., 2011).

Ex vivo bioadhesion strength

Bioadhesion strength of tablets were evaluated using a microprocessor based on advanced force gauge equipped with a motorized test stand (Ultra Test Tensile strength tester, Mecmesin, West Sussex, UK) according to method describe as it is fitted with 25kg load cell, in this test porcine membrane was secured tightly to a circular stainless steel adaptor and the buccal tablet to be tested was adhered to another cylindrical stainless steel adaptor similar in diameter using a cyanoacrylate bioadhesive. Mucin 100 μ L of 1 % w/v solution was spread over the surface of the buccal mucosa and the tablet immediately brought in contact with the mucosa. At the end of the contact time, upper support was withdrawn at 0.5mm/sec until the tablet was completely detached from the mucosa. The work of adhesion was determined from the area under the force distance curve (Liechty et al., 2010):

Swelling Studies:

Buccal tablets were weighed individually (designated as W_1) and placed separately in petri dishes containing 5 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) solution. At regular intervals (1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 hrs), the buccal tablets were removed from the petridishes and excess surface water was removed carefully using the filter paper. The swollen tablets were then reweighed (W_2). This experiment was performed in triplicate.

Surface pH

The bioadhesive tablets were allowed to swell by keeping it in contact with 1 mL of distilled water for 2hr at room temperature. The pH was measured by bringing the pH – meter electrode, in contact with the surface of tablet and allowing it to equilibrate for 1 min.

Ex vivo residence time

The *Ex vivo* residence time is one of the important physical parameter of buccal mucoadhesive tablet. The adhesive tablet was pressed over excised pig mucosa for 30sec after previously being secured on glass slab and was immersed in a basket of the dissolution apparatus containing around 500 ml of phosphate buffer, pH 6.8, at 37°C. The paddle of the dissolution apparatus as adjusted at a distance of 5 cm from the tablet and rotated at 25 rpm. The time for complete erosion or detachment from the mucosa was recorded.

Moisture absorption :

Agar (5% m/V) was dissolved in hot water. It was transferred into Petri dishes and allowed to solidify. Three buccal tablets from each formulation were placed in a vacuum oven overnight prior to the study to remove moisture, if any, and laminated on one side with a water impermeable backing membrane. They were then placed on the surface of the agar and incubated at 37°C for one hour. Then the tablets were removed and weighed and the percentage of moisture absorption was calculated by using following formula:

Kinetic modeling of dissolution data

The dissolution profile of all factorial batches were fitted to various models such as zero order, first order, Higuchi, Hixon Crowell, Korsmeyer and Peppas, to ascertain the kinetic of drug release. The method described by Korsmeyer and Peppas was used to describe mechanism of drug release.

Short-term stability study

To determine change in bioadhesive strength and *in vitro* release profile on storage, a short-term stability study of the optimal batch was performed at 40°C in humidity jar with 75% relative humidity (RH). Samples were withdrawn at 1-month intervals and evaluated for any change in bioadhesive strength and *in vitro* drug release pattern.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation study:

Preformulation studies are primarily done to investigate the physicochemical properties of drug and to establish its compatibility with other excipients used.

FTIR Compatibility Studies:

FTIR spectra of pure drug and formulation with other ingredients were recorded. The FTIR Spectra of pure Lesinurad drug and polymer was compared with the FTIR spectrum of drug and optimised in the figures, respectively.

Fig.1:FTIR for Pure Drug.

Fig.2: FTIR for optimized formulations.

There was no appearance or disappearance of any characteristics peak in the FTIR spectrum of drug and the polymers used. This shows that there is no chemical interaction between the drug and the polymers used. The presence of peaks at the expected range confirms that the materials taken for the study are genuine and there were no possible interactions.

Characterisation of Precompression Blend:

The precompression blend for Buccal tablets were characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index and drug content and shown in the Table. Angle of repose was less than 30° and Carr's index values were less than 18 for the precompression blend of all the batches indicating good to fair flowability and compressibility, Hausner's ratio was less than 1.25 for all the batches indicating good flow properties.

Table 2: Physical Properties of Precompression Blend.

Formulation Code	Angle of repose (θ)	Bulk density (g/mL)	Tapped density(g/mL)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	26.76 \pm 1.2	0.526 \pm 1.8	0.612 \pm 1.6	14.0 \pm 0.02	1.16 \pm 0.1
F2	27.54 \pm 2.5	0.662 \pm 1.2	0.763 \pm 1.3	13.23 \pm 0.1	1.15 \pm 0.05
F3	24.65 \pm 2.5	0.695 \pm 1.5	0.823 \pm 0.8	15.5 \pm 0.08	1.18 \pm 0.1
F4	22.9 \pm 1.4	0.672 \pm 1.2	0.742 \pm 1.2	12.2 \pm 0.1	1.21 \pm 0.2
F5	28.3 \pm 2.2	0.643 \pm 2.1	0.624 \pm 0.7	14.2 \pm 0.9	1.11 \pm 0.2
F6	24.84 \pm 0.4	0.654 \pm 1.6	0.755 \pm 1.4	13.12 \pm 1.8	1.12 \pm 0.06
F7	28.68 \pm 0.8	0.782 \pm 1.2	0.869 \pm 0.8	11.0 \pm 1.2	1.11 \pm 0.2
F8	24.68 \pm 1.2	0.560 \pm 0.5	0.631 \pm 1.2	11.25 \pm 0.15	1.12 \pm 0.08
F9	25.16 \pm 0.8	0.628 \pm 2.5	0.714 \pm 1.6	14.27 \pm 0.12	1.17 \pm 0.5

Each value represents the mean \pm SD ($n=3$).

PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF BUCCAL TABLETS:

Physicochemical parameters

The average weight of the tablet was found to be between 448.12 \pm 0.80 to 450.74 \pm 0.61mg. The maximum variation from average was found to be \pm 2.30% from all the formulations. Hardness of the tablets for all the formulations was found to be between 6.47 \pm 0.06 to 7.47 \pm 0.21kg/cm². Percentage friability for all formulations was found to be between 0.04 and 0.91 with an average of 0.48. Percentage drug content for all formulations was found to be between 99.39% and 101.94%. Thickness of buccal tablets of all the formulations was found to be between 1.63 \pm 0.015 to 1.89 \pm 0.012. It was concluded that the tablets would produce no local irritation to the mucosal surface. All these results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Physico-chemical parameters of Lesinurad buccal tablets:

Formulation Code	Average Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Assay (%)
F1	450.74 \pm 0.61	1.81 \pm 0.012	7.30 \pm 0.17	0.04	100.71 \pm 0.99
F2	450.04 \pm 0.80	1.86 \pm 0.010	6.70 \pm 0.20	0.48	101.94 \pm 0.86
F3	449.38 \pm 0.71	1.80 \pm 0.015	7.03 \pm 0.15	0.51	101.35 \pm 3.20
F4	450.65 \pm 0.64	1.66 \pm 0.021	7.43 \pm 0.15	0.91	100.10 \pm 1.88
F5	449.91 \pm 1.01	1.77 \pm 0.015	6.57 \pm 0.20	0.05	99.72 \pm 2.18
F6	449.98 \pm 0.82	1.89 \pm 0.012	7.03 \pm 0.32	0.88	99.82 \pm 3.00
F7	448.12 \pm 0.80	1.65 \pm 0.015	7.47 \pm 0.21	0.49	101.65 \pm 1.56
F8	450.04 \pm 0.71	1.72 \pm 0.015	6.47 \pm 0.06	0.04	99.48 \pm 2.39
F9	449.94 \pm 0.75	1.63 \pm 0.015	6.90 \pm 0.27	0.89	99.39 \pm 2.08

Each value represents the mean \pm SD ($n=3$).

In vitro drug release studies

In vitro drug release studies were conducted in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and the studies revealed that the release of Lesinurad from different formulations varies with characteristics and composition of matrix forming polymers as shown in graphs.

Tablets formulated using Sodium Alginate, Carbopol 934 and Sodium CMC alone were eroded faster & dissolved completely within 1-2 hrs. While tablets remain intactness and provide slow drug release up to 8 hrs.

As increase in the polymer concentration, causes an increase in the viscosity of the gel as well as formation of a gel layer with a longer diffusion path and decrease in diffusion coefficient of drug. Therefore, increased in polymers concentration leads to decrease in drug release. This was observed that there was a reduction in the amount of polymer ensures faster release. This may be attributed due to reduction in strength of gel layer which enhances drug diffusion and water uptake through matrix.

Table 4: *In vitro* cumulative percentage drug release profile of Lesinurad formulations with Sodium alginate.

Time (hrs)	Cumulative percentage drug release		
	F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0
1	28.15	35.11	31.78
2	40.24	64.31	45.65
3	46.72	76.39	49.74
4	51.31	81.10	53.41
5	58.39	86.32	58.98
6	63.38	90.25	63.38
7	69.84	94.31	69.10
8	73.54	99.87	80.36

Fig.3: *In vitro* cumulative % drug release of Lesinurad buccal tablets with Sodium Alginate.Table 5: *In vitro* cumulative percentage drug release profile of Lesinurad formulations with Sodium CMC.

Time (hrs)	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0
1	54.57	26.65	19.31
2	63.12	41.34	32.38
3	71.34	46.81	39.41
4	76.14	55.74	45.25
5	82.41	61.47	52.31
6	88.54	65.74	64.52
7	93.14	78.14	77.54
8	98.97	89.47	84.54

Each value represents the mean \pm SD (n=3).

Fig.4: *In vitro* cumulative % drug release of Lesinurad buccal tablets with Sodium CMC.

Table 6: *In vitro* cumulative percentage drug release profile of Lesinurad formulations with Carbopol 934.

Time (hrs)	Cumulative percentage drug release		
	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0
1	24.25	28.72	48.47
2	44.32	35.48	61.34
3	52.87	41.65	68.45
4	58.23	48.67	74.38
5	64.85	55.45	83.74
6	69.41	63.54	89.68
7	76.37	78.65	95.18
8	90.58	88.95	98.85

Fig.5: *In vitro* cumulative % drug release of Lesinurad buccal tablets with Carbopol 934.

Formulation F2 (99.87) composed of 1:0.25 (drug: Sodium Alginate) ratio, F4 (98.97) composed of 1: 0.25 (drug: Sodium CMC) ratio, F9 (98.85) composed of 1:0.5 (drug: Carbopol 934P) ratio showed maximum % drug release among their respective series. Finally it was concluded that, *In vitro* drug release studies revealed that the release of Lesinurad from different formulations varied according to the type and ratios of the matrix forming polymers.

Swelling Studies of buccal tablets

Appropriate swelling property of a buccal device is essential for uniform and prolonged release of drug and proper bioadhesion. The polymeric tablet formulations displayed an increase in weight due to water uptake. The mucoadhesive polymers (Sodium Alginate gum, Carbopol 934 and Sodium CMC) used in this study were hydrogels which are swellable upon contact with water and retain large amount of water. Swelling behavior of buccal tablets of all formulations as a function of time is shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6: Swelling studies of buccal tablets.

Moisture absorption test:

The moisture absorption studies give an indication of the relative moisture absorption capacities of polymers and whether the formulations maintain their integrity after moisture absorption.

Ex vivo residence time:

The *Ex vivo* residence time is one of the important physical parameter of buccal mucoadhesive tablets. The *ex vivo* residence time was determined by using specially designed apparatus. As the concentration of mucoadhesive material increased, the residence time increased. This test reflects the adhesive capacity of polymers used in formulations. The results revealed that the Sodium alginate containing formulations showed better residence time than the other polymer formulations shown in Table7.

Ex vivo bioadhesive strength measurement:

The values of the bioadhesive strength of Lesinurad buccal tablets of different formulations were given in Table. The bioadhesive characters were found to be affected by the nature and proportions of the bioadhesive polymers used in the formulations.

Hence the formulation with optimized bioadhesive strength should be chosen i.e. formulation containing Sodium alginate.

Table 7: *Ex vivo* residence time, Moisture absorption, Surface pH, Bioadhesive strength values of Lesinurad buccal tablets.

Formulation code	<i>Ex vivo</i> residence time	Moisture absorbance	Surface pH	Bioadhesive strength	
				Peak detachment force (N)	Work of adhesion (mJ)
F1	5 Hrs 15 min	30.83± 0.25	6.96±0.16	1.89±0.55	0.47±0.28
F2	5Hrs 42 min	25.66 ± 0.25	6.86±0.43	2.34±0.02	0.62±0.04
F3	5Hrs 45 min	32.45 ± 0.25	6.9±0.35	2.05±0.42	0.5±0.28
F4	5 Hrs 35 min	17.51 ± 0.30	6.5±0.12	1.24±0.38	0.34±0.17
F5	5 Hrs 20 min	9.61±0.25	6.66±0.23	2.42±0.06	0.74±0.02
F6	5 Hrs 15 min	20.83±0.25	7.43±0.15	1.30±0.12	0.40±0.38
F7	6Hrs 10 min	14.16±0.25	6.8±0.43	2.30±0.26	0.61±0.13
F8	6 Hrs 15 min	13.33±0.30	6.77±0.24	2.68±0.03	0.95±0.08
F9	7Hrs 45 min	19.16±0.30	6.67±0.13	2.44±0.47	0.69±0.41

CONCLUSION

Development of bioadhesive buccal drug delivery of repaglinide tablets is one of the alternatives routes of administration to avoid first pass metabolism and provide prolonged release. In addition, these formulations reduce the need of frequent administration and enhance patient compliance. A combination of HPMC K15M and Chitosan results in sustained release buccal drug delivery. The buccal bilayer tablet showed a mucoadhesion time of more than 12 h. Similarly, *in vitro* permeation studies showed 84.43% ± 3.68% drug release of the sustained dosage form, which can be used in once a day tablet.

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